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RURAL MARKET IN INDIA: OPPORTUNITIES, CHALLENGES AND MARKETING STRATEGIES

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ABSTRACT

The market scenario in the rural areas today is changing very rapidly. Rural consumers demand branded products mainly because of increase in disposable income and literacy level. In the present paper we tried to indentify the opportunities, challenges and marketing strategies to overcome these challenges. The present study is based on secondary data collected from various sources such as websites, case studies, academic journals, and business magazines and reviewed various research papers on rural market in order to understand the role and characteristics of rural market, characteristics and purchasing behaviour of rural consumer and various marketing strategies that can be used to capture the untapped potential of rural market. After analyzing the challenges and opportunities in rural market we found that there are vast untapped opportunities are available in rural India. But marketers are unable to tap these opportunities because of lack of infrastructure facilities. Literacy rate is low in rural area so people are unable to identify brand difference. Language differences, culture, believes, traditional outlook, seasonal demands, socio-economic backwardness, inadequate media coverage etc. creates problems for marketers.

Keyword: Rural Market, Brand, opportunities, Literacy.

Introduction: In recent years, rural markets have acquired significance, as the overall growth of the economy has resulted in substantial increase in the purchasing power of the rural communities. On account of green revolution, the rural areas have started consuming a large quantity of industrial and urban manufactured products. In this context, a special marketing strategy has emerged which is called rural marketing. The concept of rural marketing in India economy has always played an influential role in the lives of people.

The Indian rural market with its vast size and heterogeneous demand base offers great lucrative opportunities to marketers. After all, two thirds of the countries' consumers live in rural areas and almost half of the national income is generated in the rural hinterland. India is classified into around 450 districts, and approximately 6,30,000 villages, which can be segmented in different parameters such as literacy levels, accessibility, distribution networks, income levels, market penetration, distances from nearest towns, etc. Recent developments, which has taken place in the rural areas under the five- year plans and other such special programs, are phenomenal. The overall growth of the economy has resulted into substantial increase in the purchasing power of the rural communities.

Today the rural market offers a vast untapped potential. Development programs in the field of agriculture and related activities such as health education; communication, rural electrification, etc have improved the lifestyles of village population. Rural India, which accounts for more than 70 per cent of the country's one billion population (according to the Census of India 2001), is not just

witnessing an increase in its income but also in consumption and production. It is in this background that rural marketing has emerged as a special marketing strategy. As rural markets acquire significance the Indian growth story spreads itself to India's hinterlands.

In other words, The Rural Market has truly arrived.

Phases in Rural Marketing

Part1 (before 1960's) It was completely an unorganized market where “baniyas and mahajans” dominate the market. Rural marketing was another word for agriculture marketing because, agriculture produces like food grains and industries like cotton, oil seeds, etc. occupied primary attention.

Part2 (1960 to 1990) The greatest thing that happened in this period was green revolution, which led to farming, involves scientific and technological methods and many poor villages become prosperous business centers. Rural marketing meant “marketing of agriculture inputs” and “agriculture marketing”. Agencies like khadi and village industries commissions bloomed and government paid attention to promote these products.

Part3 (after Mid 1990) Since 1990, India's industrial sector had gain strength and maturity. Its contribution to GNP increased substantially. With support and development programs of center and state government rural area progressed socially and economically and emerges as a new market. Rural marketing was considered different from agriculture marketing.

What makes rural marketing attractive?

- Untapped rural potential
- 6,27,000 villages across the country
- Account for 70% of population
- 60% of national demand for various Product categories

Rationale of Study: Rural market is huge. Rural population has been increased by 9% from 2001 to 2011 and comprises of 833 million people as compare to 377 million people in urban area, which shows greater opportunities for marketers.

Rural India has a population of 83.3 crore (Table) spread across 6, 38,000 villages. The rural urban distribution ratio currently is 68.84% and 31.16% respectively.

Rural market is getting importance because of the saturation of urban market. Marketers are looking for extending their product categories to an unexplored market i.e. the rural market. According to the Nielson's survey the rural market for FMCG (Rs. 65,000 crores), durables (Rs. 5,000 crores) and clothing and footwear (Rs. 35,000 crores) was as large as Rs. 1, 05,000 crores in 2008. Certainly the size is much bigger now. According to Nielson by 2025, the rural FMCG sale is estimated to be \$ 100 billion from the current \$ 12 billion.

Rural market is mystery for the companies. Due to lack of dipper insights into the psyche of the rural consumers, companies are hesitant to explore this territory. But local brand like “Ghadi” detergent in Kanpur have been able successfully tap the opportunities presented by rural market.

Rural India offers sustainable sales and profit for growth. Growth of rural market is possible due to green revolution and white revolution, which results into substantial wealth generation in rural area. In recent years, rural markets have acquired significance in the country like China and India as the overall growth of the economy has resulted into substantial increase purchasing power of rural communities.

Rural market status

The market scenario in the rural areas today is changing very rapidly. Rural consumers demand branded products mainly because of increase in disposable income and literacy level. Rural families do not like to cut their expenditure on weddings, pilgrimages, constructions and consumptions. Rural consumers have more aspirations, today this segment of buyers consumes large variety of products, both durable and non-durables and willing to pay right price for right products.

Rural share in stock of consumer demands

Demand	1995-96 (in '000)	Share in percent	2001-02 (in '000)	2009-10 (in '000)	Share in percent
Cars/Jeeps	6	2.1	63	376	10.9
Motorcycle	359	47.3	1036	4045	48.3
Scooters	368	33.1	355	311	39.9
Mopeds	286	52.7	235	141	57.7
Automotive	1016	37.9	1689	4873	37.9
Television	4852	54.0	6400	7712	44.2
All Fans	7050	50.0	14627	32561	56.7

Source: The Great India Market, National Council of Applied Economics Research

The table shows that the rural share in stock of consumer demands. The rural share in demand for car/jeeps has increased from 2.1% in 1995-96 to 8.0% in 2001-02 and 10.9% in 2009-10 and for motorcycle it has increased from 47.3% in 1995-96 to 48.3% in 2009-10. Similarly, the demand of fans, scooter, moped and low cost items has also increased. Share of automotive remained same at 37.9%. Thus it is clear from the table that the percentage of rural share in the stock of consumer demands has been raising since 1995-96 to 2009-10.

Difference in the rural urban demand (consumables)

Items		2001-02 (figures in '000)	2009-10 (figures in '000)	Percentage Increase (%)
Shampoos	Urban	13.6	31.4	130.8
	Rural	6.7	16.3	143.2
Edible Oil	Urban	2328.0	3986.5	71.24
	Rural	4681.6	666.2	42.3

Source: The Great India Market, National Council of Applied Economics Research

From the table we can see that percentage increase in demand shampoos, health beverages, toilet shop, washing cakes and washing powder is more in rural areas as compare to urban area. While in edible oil and packed biscuits increase in demand is more in urban area as compare to rural area. Thus we can say that the consumption of many items areas is increasing at a high speed and higher than the growing demand in urban area.

Thus the study of rural market, its characteristics, rural consumers and their purchasing behavior is very important.

Objective of the Study: in the present research paper we tried to indentify the opportunities and challenge in rural market. The various marketing strategies have been also explored to overcome these challenges in rural market.

Research Methodology: This research paper is an attempt to show the importance of rural marketing and various marketing strategies to utilize the opportunities offered by rural market. The present study is based on secondary data collected from various sources such as websites, case studies, academic journals, and business magazines and reviewed various research papers on rural market in order to understand the role and characteristics of rural market, characteristics and purchasing

behavior of rural consumer and various marketing strategies that can be used to capture the untapped potential of rural market.

Opportunities in Rural Market:

The rural market has been growing gradually over the past few years and is now even bigger than the urban market. The saving to income percentage in rural area is 30% higher than urban area. At present 53% of all FMCGs and 59% of consumers durables are being sold in rural area. Major opportunities available in rural market are as follow:

Huge untapped Potential: As more than 70% of the total India’s population dwells in rural areas, the huge population itself speaks of its potential. The rural market offers a great chance for different branded goods as well as services for large number of customers. Penetration levels for many products are low in rural areas. The market has been growing at 3-4% per annum adding more than one million new consumers every year.

Impact of globalization: Globalization had a great impact on target groups like farmers, youth and women. Farmers, today 'keep in touch' with the latest information and maximize both ends. On youth its impact is on knowledge and information and while on women it still depends on the socio-economic aspect. The marketers who understand the rural consumer and fine tune their strategy are sure to reap benefits.

Effectiveness of communication: An important tool to reach out to the rural audience is through effective communication. The rural audience has matured enough to understand the communication developed for the urban markets, especially with reference to FMCG products. Television has been a major effective communication system for rural mass and, as a result, companies should identify themselves with their advertisements.

Increase in literacy rate

	2001	2011	Difference
Overall India	64.8	74.0	+9.2
Rural	58.7	68.9	+10.2
Urban	79.9	85.0	+5.1

Source: census of India 2011

Literacy rate is increasing in rural areas. There are more graduates in rural than in urban India. This brings social and cultural changes in buying behavior of the rural customers and more aware about national and international brand. Due to increase in literacy rate they get jobs in nearby towns. They earn urban salaries but continue to live in self owned homes in the villages, they have high purchasing power and prefer to buy branded product.

Increasing in disposable income and purchasing power : Projects from private companies and the rural employment initiatives by the Government like MNREGA (Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act) schemes have given the rural population an opportunity to meet their daily needs. Government decided to expand the agriculture loan at lower rate of interest and distribute million of Kisan Credit Cards, has given a boost to the income level to the rural sector. According to advanced estimates of national income released by center statistic organization “The Per Capita income at current prices during 2011-12 is estimated to be Rs. 60,972 compared to Rs. 53,332 during 2010-11 showing a rise of 14.3%. Companies have the opportunity to enter in this new market and take the advantage of increased disposable income.

Change in rural consumer behaviour: With the economic development of rural areas, disposable income of rural people has gone up. Moreover, with the presence of Internet and direct-to-home television connectivity in rural areas, these people have started gaining knowledge about the different brands that are available in urban markets. They are slowly realizing the importance of established brands and have started purchasing these brands. Rural people are now purchasing branded soaps, toothpowder, paste, tobacco products, radio, TV, bicycles, motorcycles, cooking utensils, wrist watch, razor blades, detergents and so on. It is a boon to the companies that rural people amidst deficiency spend so lavishly on weddings, ceremonies, rituals and festivals..

Favorable government policies: As a part of the process of planned economic development, the government has been making concerted efforts towards rural development. The massive investment in the rural India has generated new employment, new income and new purchasing power. In the recent years, as a part of new farming policies, high support prices are offered for agricultural products. Various measures like tax exemption in rural areas, subsidy, concessions, incentives, assistances, literacy drive in rural areas has bought in rapid development of rural markets. Government's initiative for vocationalization of education especially in rural areas comes as a major boost in rural areas.

Credit facilities through banks: With co-operative banks taking the lead in the rural areas, every village has access to short, medium, long-term loans from these banks. The credit facilities extended by public sector banks through rural financing schemes like Kisaan Credit Cards help the farmers to buy seeds, fertilizers and consumer durable goods on installments. The introduction of the micro finance proved to be of great help to the people living in hinterlands.

Intense Competition in urban markets :Intensified competition in urban markets is leading to increase in costs and thereby reducing market share. The rural markets are therefore becoming increasingly attractive in comparison to urban markets. The automobile and FMCG market brings this out clearly. Hero Honda motorcycles, Parle, Britannia, Brooke Bond, Maruti Cars, HLL products or Wipro products find ready acceptance in rural markets as compared to urban markets where there is a proliferation of brands.

Reduction of Risk during Recession: It has been observed that companies which cater both urban and rural markets tackle the recession in the better way. The demands for goods in the urban market often follow a cyclic whereas in the rural market it is steady. So companies can safeguard themselves from the harmful effects of recession after entering in the rural market.

IT Penetration in Rural India: Today's rural children and youth will grow up in an environment where they have information access to education opportunities, job opportunities, government schemes, worldwide news and mandi prices. Rural areas offer a great potential for growth in internet usage with the number of claimed internet users in these spaces to be reached at 45 million by Dec. 2012

Infrastructure improving rapidly: In 50 years only, 40% villages have been connected by roads, in next 10 years another 30% would be connected. Rural telephone density has gone up by 300% in the last 10 years. Government of India is planning its most ambitious national program in Jan.2013 to facilitate electricity through decentralized renewable energy sources. The government aims to provide LED lights to around 400million homes that do not have an electricity connection by 2017. Rapid development of rural infrastructure is also major attraction for marketers. Marketers can make effective use of the large available infrastructure-

Increase Population and hence Increase in Demand: The rural market in India is vast and

Post Offices	1,38,000
Haats (periodic markets)	42,000
Melas (exhibitions)	25,000
Mandis (agro markets)	7,000
Public Distribution Shops	3,80,000
Bank Branches	32,000

Source: Commissioner ate of Rural Development, Government

scattered and offers a plethora of opportunities in comparison to the urban sector. It covers the maximum population and regions and thereby, the maximum number of consumers. More than eighty percent of rural markets in India still do not have access to any sort of organized marketing and distribution. So there is a sea of opportunities for retailers to serve the consumers in rural and semi urban India. CRISIL study estimates that over 60% of India’s population would be residing in rural area in 2026

Low Penetration Rate

Penetration rate in rural India is very low.

Durables	Urban	Rural	Total(%of rural HH)
CTV	30.4	4.8	12.1
Refrigerator	33.5	3.5	12.0
FMCGs	Urban	Rural	Total(%of rural HH)
Shampoo	66.3	35.2	44.2
Toothpaste	82.2	44.9	55.6

Source: NCAER’s Market Information Survey of Households

The table above shows the rural and urban share in stock of consumer durables like Color T.V and refrigerator and FMCGs like shampoo and toothpaste. It is clear from the table that penetration rate in rural market is low as compared to urban market; low penetration indicates the existence of unsaturated markets, which are likely to expand as the income level rise as well as awareness increases. It provides an excellent opportunity for the industry players in form of vastly untapped market.

Remittances from family members working in urban areas : At least one of the family members from almost every rural family is works in city. They remit their salaries back home to their family members residing in rural areas. These remittances are a sizeable contribution to growing rural income & purchasing power of rural people.

Challenges in Rural Market

1. Deprived people and deprived markets: The number of people below the poverty line has not decreased in any appreciable manner. Thus, poor people and consequently underdevel-oped markets characterize rural markets. A vast majority of rural people is tradition bound, and they also face

problems such as inconsistent electrical power, scarce infrastructure and unreliable telephone system, and politico-business associations that hinder development efforts.

2. Lack of communication facilities: Even today, most villages in the country are inaccessible during the monsoons. A large number of villages in the country have no access to telephones. Other communication infrastructure is also highly underdeveloped.

3. Transport: Many rural areas are not connected by rail transport. Many roads have been poorly surfaced and got severely damaged during monsoons. The use of bullock carts is inevitable even today. Camel carts are used in Rajasthan and Gujarat in both rural and urban sectors.

4. Many languages and dialects: The languages and dialects vary from state to state, region to region and probably from district to district. Since messages have to be delivered in the local language, it is difficult for the marketers to design promotional strategies for each of these areas. Facilities such as phone, telegram and fax are less developed in villages adding to the communication problems faced by the marketers.

5. Dispersed markets: Rural population is scattered over a large land area. And it is almost impossible to ensure the availability of a brand all over the country. District fairs are periodic and occasional in nature. Manufacturers and retailers prefer such occasions, as they allow greater visibility and capture the attention of the target audience for larger spans of time. Advertising in such a highly heterogeneous market is also very expensive.

6. Low per capita income: The per capita income of rural people is low as compared to the urban people. Moreover, demand in rural markets depends on the agricultural situation, which in turn depends on the monsoons. Therefore, the demand is not stable or regular. Hence, the per-capita income is low in villages compared with urban areas.

7. Low levels of literacy The level of literacy is lower compared with urban areas. This again leads to a problem of communication in these rural areas. Print medium becomes ineffective and to an extent irrelevant, since its reach is poor.

8. Prevalence of spurious brands and seasonal demand: For any branded product, there are a multitude of local variants, which are cheaper and hence more desirable. Also, due to illiteracy, the consumer can hardly make out a spurious brand from an original one. Rural consumers are cautious in buying and their decisions are slow, they generally give a product a trial and only after complete satisfaction they buy it again.

9. Different way of thinking: There is a vast difference in the lifestyles of the people. The choice of brands that an urban customer enjoys is not available to the rural customer, who usually has two to three choices. As such, the rural customer has a fairly simple thinking and their decisions are still governed by customs and traditions. It is difficult to make them adopt new practices.

10. Warehousing problem: Warehousing facilities in the form of godowns are not available in rural India. The available godowns are not properly maintained to keep goods in proper conditions. This is a major problem because of which the warehousing cost increases in rural India

11. Problems in sales force management: Sales force is generally reluctant to work in rural areas. The languages and dialects vary from state to state, region to region, and probably from district to district. Since messages have to be delivered in the local language, it is difficult for sales force to communicate with the rural consumers. Sales force finds it difficult to adjust to the rural environment and inadequate facilities available in rural areas.

12. Distribution problem: Effective distribution requires village-level shopkeeper, toluka-level wholesaler/dealer, district-level stockist/distributor, and company-owned depot at state level. These many tiers increase the cost of distribution.

Rural markets typically signify complex logistical challenges that directly translate into high distribution costs. Bad roads, inadequate warehousing and lack of good distributors pose as major problems to the marketers.

Marketing Strategies for Rural Marketing

1) Product strategy

In India, rural market is relatively special, which has the different consumer community, located in the different physiographic region and the different consumer community, has the difference consumer demand. Therefore, when a company launches product for the rural market, they should pay great attention to meet the rural consumer's need.

Positioning: Product positioning plays a crucial role in marketing of rural products. Marketer has to position their products after understanding the unique characteristics of the rural market environment. Companies can reposition their existing products in rural markets. For example, refrigerator-manufacturing companies can launch a refrigerator of bigger size because most of the families in rural areas are joint, big families and they require big refrigerators having bigger storage capacity. Secondly in India most of the villages are facing acute shortage of water; here companies can reposition their washing machine, which require less water than any ordinary washing machine.

Segmentation And Targeting - Right segmentation and targeting principles are key to achieve faster success in rural market. Most firms assume that rural markets are homogeneous. It is unwise on the part of these firms to assume that the rural market can be served with the same product, price and promotion combination. Segmentation can be done based on one or more variables like demographic (income, education, lifestyle, gender, marital status, family size, occupation and religion), geographic, psychographic (social class, life style and personality) and behavioral aspects (occasions, benefit sought, user status, usage rate, loyalty status, place and product possession category).

Packaging - As far as packaging is concerned, as a general rule, smaller packages are more popular in the rural areas. The lower income group consumers are not able to purchase large and medium size packaged goods. It is also found that the labeling on the package is not in the local language. This is a major constraint to rural consumers understanding the product characteristics. Hence, companies should take into consideration proper packaging and the size of the packs before diffusing their products in rural areas. Many FMCG companies have introduced smaller pack sizes to increase category penetration. For example, the products like shampoos, soaps, hair-oil, toothpaste, spices, pickles, jams, ketchups, tea, coffee sachets, confectionery products, medicated products like Vicks, pain-relieving ointments, etc.

Product customization strategy - The following strategies could be in line with product customization strategy.

i) Straight extension strategy -In straight extension strategy, the same product could be marketed to the rural customers with minimum or least modifications; i.e. the contents remain the same but say, the packs may differ. E.g. the products like FMCG could be marketed in small packs or sachets like hair oil, toothpaste, washing powder, shampoo, etc.

ii) Product adoption strategy - The product adoption strategy states that the products are modified to suit the specific need of the corresponding segment. E.g. a torch provided in the mobile phone marketed among rural customers.

iii) Backward invention strategy - This strategy involves selling less complex and simple products. E.g. electric sewing machines are introduced in urban markets and manually operating machines in rural markets.

iv) Forward invention strategy - This strategy includes developing entirely new products for the rural customers. E.g. introducing a tractor as a product for rural customers.

2) Price strategy: Pricing strategies are very much linked to product strategies. With low disposable incomes, products need to be affordable to the rural consumer, most of which are on daily wages.. Some of these pricing strategies are mentioned below –

Focusing on volume not margins: A significant portion of the rural population is paid daily wages. Daily wage earners tend to have little stock of money, and, therefore, tend to make purchases only to meet their daily needs. Therefore, the marketing strategies in rural India must be to concentrate on large volumes over low margins and thus the overall profitability can be maintained.

Lower prices: Consumers in the rural areas are highly price conscious. They tend to purchase only those products, which are inexpensive in nature, may it be local brands. Moreover, companies have adopted an unwritten policy to dump second grade quality products to sell them at lower prices in the rural market.

Credit facility: This holds true for marketing of consumer durable and automobiles. As the purchasing power of the rural customer is quite low, they tend to purchase high-ended products on credit. The companies should make use of this opportunity to sell products. They have started collaborating with banks and other financial institutions to sell their expensive products on credit.

3) Distribution Strategy: Studies reveal that the bigger villages of above 5000 population are fairly covered by the marketing people of various companies manufacturing consumable and durable products. The smaller villages are not fully touched due to various reasons like accessibility, small markets and far distances from towns and villages. Strategies for distribution to various rural segments are discussed as under:

Small Villages: In order to reach smaller villages, two types of strategies have to be adopted i.e., reach all villages above 2000 population and reach all those within 50 km radius of big towns and cities. This will help cover about 50% of the rural population and even this extent of coverage means approximately 350 million populations and this is a massive coverage. Very small villages below 500 populations can be ignored at this stage, as the output will not compensate the input. There should be distribution vans to cover villages on fixed period (at least once a week) so that the shopkeepers as well as the public are sure of supplies from the feeder centre, which will be nearby a town or city.

Activating Co-operative Societies: Though cooperatives have been started mainly for input and output of rural produce, there is scope and possibility to use these premises and offices for marketing of consumer goods to rural people throughout India. There are more than three lakh cooperative offices working under different names like - marketing cooperatives, credit cooperative society, farmers' service cooperative societies and various local level cooperatives. The premises and manpower can be better utilized by introducing the consumer, durables and consumables required by the rural population.

Utilizing P.D.S Stores and Petrol Pumps: These are two unexplored areas to develop market. Public Distribution Systems (PDS) are available throughout the country and even in villages. Similarly petrol pumps are available on all highways, state highways and link roads to towns and big villages. In rural areas the petrol pumps and PDS stores have adequate spare time to attend additional functions.

Towns as Feeder Centers: Towns are frequently visited by rural people for education, cinema, dramas, purchases, medical treatment and various functions. It will be convenient if the town market is used as a distribution channel for various villages surrounding towns. One or two traders in town need to be used as feeders to village stores and also to sell directly to villagers coming to towns.

4) Promotion Strategy

Since the literary level of rural population is low, it pays to do promotions through mass media like TV, cinema and radio advertisements. In print media, mostly hoardings and wall paintings will help more. These promotional strategies are covered as under:

Cinema: For the last 60 years, cinema continues to be influencing factors in style, tastes, dress materials and total Indian culture. The effect of cinema is much more in Southern India than elsewhere. In the South, 76 % rural people view cinema regularly whereas elsewhere it is around 25 %. Product advertisements before a movie and during intervals get good publicity. All the theaters do this with the help of slides and 1 or 2 minutes movie type advertisements to highlight the product performance and utility. This method will continue to be popular as many villagers like to see movies in theatres than on TV.

Television: Since the last two decades, TV viewing has been a regular pastime for all Indian public. In fact, Doordarshan covers 85 % of India and private channels have started operating at continental, national and regional levels. The advertisers have choice of segment to be touched. For all India coverage, important and popular serial intervals are best to advertise on TV..

Radio: The first and most famous commercial on Radio was BinacaGeethmala on Radio Ceylon. Subsequently, many programmes have come on –VividhaBharati and local languages. Film songs are popular and playing advertisements in between to attract attention by the listeners. Coverage of radio stations is wide and serves the purpose. About 75 % of the rural population listens occasionally.

Print Media: Due to low literacy rate and poor reading habits, this is not a popular promotion strategy. However, some advertisements are made through the local language low priced dailies. Rural people normally read newspapers on Fridays and Sundays when there is more coverage about the movies being shown and the forth-coming movies. So the promotion of cinema viewing is best done by the newspapers as far as rural people are concerned.

Hoardings: Hoardings on village entry junctions, writing and painting on walls of public buildings in villages, compound walls of private people will be more appealing and readable. The rural inputs like fertilizers and pesticides are advertised like this. The picture of product and catchy slogans are considered to be the best promoters.

Village Congregations/ Gatherings: Certain places have specific market days that can be used for mass communication to speed awareness of products. Similarly particular places have local deities and Jathra or fairs along the festival type celebrations. These occasions help to promote sales, explanation or product awareness. If some promotional schemes are kept in those occasions, it will be a more appealing effort. On these occasions, audiovisual shows can be made for better explanations.

Conclusion of the Study: While concluding we can make out that rural India offers huge opportunities that companies can tap for their growth and development. However, companies face many challenges in tackling the rural markets. Vast untapped opportunities are available in rural India. But marketers are unable to tap these opportunities because of lack of infrastructure facilities. Literacy rate is low in rural area so people are unable to identify brand difference. Language differences, culture, believes, traditional outlook, seasonal demands, socio-economic backwardness, inadequate media coverage etc. creates problems for marketers.

Now the trend is changing as literacy rate in rural area is increasing. Number of middle and higher income household in rural India is expected to grow from 80 million to 111 million. There is rapid development in infrastructure, brand awareness among rural consumers is increased, and rural connectivity and communication technology were developed. With some technologies breakthrough in distribution and marketing of products in rural India, companies in rural market can earn more profits, market share, etc. The Rural market is a greater future prospect for the marketers and there are many opportunities available for them in rural markets if appropriate marketing strategies are applied.

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